

OFM-Assisted FR3-Band Photonic Up-Conversion: Hybrid Single-/Multi-Carrier FR3-Band Radio with Optical Frequency Synthesis and Carrier Reclamation

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ABSTRACT

We evaluate hybrid analogue/digital transmission based on adaptive modulation over point-to-point FR3-band channels characterized by frequency-flat fading. In support of low-complexity end-to-end fiber-wireless transmission, radio transport is further assisted by an 8- to 12-fold optical frequency multiplication for the purpose of carrier frequency synthesis, thus ensuring mobile fronthaul operation in a fading-agnostic low-frequency range and compatible with highly simplified opto-electronics. We will experimentally demonstrate two FR3 over-the-air modes, including an orthogonally frequency division multiplexed multi-carrier format and single-carrier binary phase-shift keyed signaling, which are accomplished over optical fronthaul budgets of more than 17 dB and in combination with carrier frequency reclamation for full-duplex single-carrier transmission using a paired FR3-band spectrum.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network densification, simplified remote radio heads (RRH) and the spectral expansion toward new frequency bands herald new opportunities for 6G radio access networks. As one of these new spectral windows, the IMT-2030 framework proposes the exploration of the upper mid-band between the sub-6GHz and mm-wave regions. This new frequency range, which is referred to as the FR3 band, offers an attractive mix between available spectrum and beneficial radio propagation characteristics with reduced fading due to intrinsic directionality and improved interference isolation [1, 2]. Moreover, it enables continuity between in- and out-door coverage [3].

To fully capitalize on this centimetric spectrum in a cost-efficient way, radio frequency (RF) management should be centralized – without need to synchronize resources at the RRH. Photonic solutions are ideally suited to accommodate this request by optically transporting radio signals to remote antenna sites [4] while further enabling the generation of high-frequency carriers [5-7]. While a combination of these techniques has been demonstrated in earlier radio-over-fiber works in support of FR2 mm-wave [8-12] and FR4/5 sub-mm/THz [13-17] radio, both of which might justify added complexity inherent to the use of optical combs, auxiliary optical (low-linewidth) sources and excessive digital oversampling, the deployment of FR3-band RRHs with lower effective data-rate offering should emphasize simplicity of the involved sub-systems as a balance towards their lower acceptable cost-per-bit. Such characteristics are often reflected by components with low electro-optic bandwidth and low power consumption – key attributes that can be found for 2-level transceivers centric to wireline deployments [18]. Moreover, fully analogue transmission that omits digital signal processing (DSP) can greatly contribute to energy efficiency.

Towards that, this work investigates a hybrid analogue/digital approach that capitalizes on frequency-flat fading in point-to-point FR3 channels to adaptively optimize resource utilization through adjusting the over-the-air (OTA) modulation scheme (Fig. 1). While a multi-carrier scheme is maintained to address faded channels, single-carrier 2-level modulation will be employed in a DSP-free manner under conditions that permit an adoption of broadband signaling. Frequency management will be centralized through generating FR3 band carriers by means of optical frequency modulation (OFM) at the RRH. OFM is a microwave photonics technique [19] that employs optical components to convert a low-frequency carrier signal into a considerably higher frequency. It omits the need for non-linear electronic devices to multiply the input frequency, which are often not available or inefficient. The adoption of OFM further enables the use of low-cost opto-electronics at the mobile fronthaul while mitigating dispersion-induced fading at the same time. Specifically, we extend our previous work on OFM for FR3-band applications [20, 21] through validating frequency-flat fading windows for point-to-point out-door FR3 links while demonstrating DSP-free bidirectional full-duplex broadband signaling with FR3-band carrier reclamation, involving compact OFM optics such as a silicon ring resonator. Compared to earlier works on radio-over-fiber transmission and optically assisted RRHs that build on either high-rate sigma-delta modulation [8], optical comb generators [22, 23] or coherent analogue optical frequency up-converters at the RRH [24], our scheme operates with GHz-class optoelectronics at the fronthaul, apart from well-established wideband PIN photoreceiver technology at the RRH. More importantly, it enables centralized RF sourcing, simplifies clock synchronization and ensures dispersion-tolerant fronthaul transmission.

The manuscript is organized as follows. Chapter II introduces the concept of dual-mode OTA transmission and characterizes

a representative FR3 channel. Chapter III presents the utilized OFM concept and its key components. Chapter IV discusses the evaluation framework, while Chapter V investigates the performance for OFM-assisted RF carrier generation, radio transmission in both OTA modes and FR3 carrier reclamation. Chapter VI concludes the findings.

Fig. 1. Fronthaul radio access utilizing centralized RF management and two distinctive over-the-air transmission modes through adaptive modulation.

II. FREQUENCY-FLAT FADING AND DUAL-MODE OTA RADIO

While analogue radio links promise considerable cost and energy savings compared to their DSP-assisted counterparts, their practical implementation typically requires equalization of the faded channel response, thereby offsetting the gains of radio-link simplification. However, time-variant fading can give rise to frequency-flat windows, enabling operation with reduced or no equalization overhead.

To evaluate the occurrence of such windows in short-range point-to-point links in the FR3 band, we deployed two antenna terminals at a roof-top location (Fig. 2(a)). The antenna sites were spaced by 63 m and employed directional horn antennas, each with a gain of 15 dBi. A vector network analyzer was connected through single-mode fiber (SMF) feeders and electro-optic converters based on a Mach-Zehnder modulator and a PIN photoreceiver, having electro-optic bandwidths of 29.8 and 29.9 GHz, respectively.

The channel response S_{21} , normalized to the peak channel transmission of the FR3 link, is shown in Figs. 2(b) and 2(c) in terms of magnitude $|S_{21}|$ and phase ϕ , respectively. For this first acquisition under clear-sky conditions, the supported frequency range is primarily determined by the WR-51 waveguide design of the utilized horn antennas. More importantly, we notice a ripple in $|S_{21}|$ and shallow fading effects over most of the frequency range. This ripple, which arises due to imperfect impedance matching and multi-path propagation, typically prevents broadband signal transmission and requires the adoption of multi-carrier modulation formats. However, there is a frequency-flat window around 16 GHz (indicated through \mathcal{E} in Fig. 2(b)) which stays stationary over longer time and the peak-to-peak deviation of the RF path loss remains ≤ 3 dB, while the corresponding spread of the group delay τ within this window, plotted in Fig. 2(d), varies between 298 to 649 ps over time. This value is sufficiently low to facilitate 1 Gb/s data transmission [25].

Fig. 2. (a) Point-to-point FR3 link and corresponding channel response in terms of (b) magnitude $|S_{21}|$, (c) phase ϕ , and (d) spread of group-delay τ within the frequency-flat window \mathcal{E} indicated by the dashed box in (a). (e) Meteorological conditions during FR3-band channel evaluation, and (f) its response with available contiguous spectrum Ψ overlaid as hatch pattern.

To confirm the availability of frequency-flat windows over a longer period that further involves link-degrading weather events such as dense fog (Fig. 2(e)), the channel response has been continuously monitored over more than three days, as reported in Fig. 2(f). We see a similar behavior that features an initially 3.7-GHz wide passband within a 6 dB roll-off. As the horizontal meteorological visibility drops to 183 m due to a fog event, the path loss increases while the overall frequency-dependent loss remains fairly stable. For example, the region around 18.7 GHz features a 1.5 – 2 GHz wide spectrally “flat” window, denoted by the hatched overlay Ψ . This window can suit the wireless transport of a 1 Gb/s signal. Even though this spectral window was not continuously available during the entire measurement duration as it faded and resurfaced, it was available during $\sim 70\%$ of the measurement.

III. OFM-ASSISTED FR3 CARRIER GENERATION

A. Concept and Signal Chain

The presence of a frequency-flat window motivates the use of adaptive modulation and coding to address an overall simplification in combination with spectral flexibility. While multi-carrier signals ensure continued communication during fading events, the switch to a simpler modulation format after probing the OTA channel for frequency-flat windows can reduce the overall power consumption. The required channel sounding can be either integrated with the radio waveform during multi-carrier format transmission [26] or performed periodically within a dedicated sub-millisecond slot while taking advantage of simpler 2-level signaling [27].

Figure 3 highlights this adaptive scheme together with photonic-assisted frequency conversion. A data signal is transported between a central office (CO) and the RRH over a fiber-based fronthaul. The RRH then converts the data signal to a FR3-band carrier frequency, over which a tail-end terminal (TET) is connected to the RRH. It does so by means of OFM – a microwave generation technique that can expand the addressable frequency space synthesized by a low-frequency seed tone f_1 , without necessitating an RF synthesizer or synchronized clocks. This low-frequency seed can be conveniently supplied through the fronthaul.

While radio transmission via multi-carrier formats such as orthogonally frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) will require a dedicated wavelength to transport the seed frequency f_1 toward the OFM (OTA mode 1 in Fig. 3), this seed can be extracted from the data signal when simple two-level modulation is used for FR3 radio transmission under favorable air-side channel conditions (OTA mode 2). This is because the fronthaul-transmitted data signal comprises all required spectral components, which can be extracted as a suitable OFM seed through use of standard clock recovery (CR) chipsets. Besides reducing the wavelength count at the fronthaul, the binary signaling inherent to this second mode of radio transmission mitigates the need for (i) linear opto-electronic converters and (ii) high-resolution analogue-to-digital conversion (ADC/DAC) stages at the

TET (see Fig. 1) – both of which being a necessity to implement the multi-carrier OFDM format. Similar approaches have been adopted for the FR4/FR5 bands, where broadband signals with simpler formats have been transported over wireless [28] and microwave plastic fibers [29]. However, there is no such investigation for the FR3 band to our best knowledge.

Fig. 3. Radio transmission over two OTA modes and signal chain, including the architecture of the OFM sub-system.

B. Optical Frequency Modulator and Demodulator

The OFM principle adopted in this work builds on optical frequency modulation (FM) and frequency-to-intensity conversion of the resulting comb before its conversion to an electrical RF carrier (see inset in Fig. 3). The periodic spectral filter that serves the optical demodulation is further tailoring the spectrum by pronouncing lines that match the desired multiplication factor M , before a conversion of the beat spectrum to the electrical domain and selection of a specific comb line through a RF bandpass filter (BPF) takes place.

Efficient optical FM generation is facilitated with a distributed Bragg reflector (DBR) laser, whose RF input is first cleaned through a narrow (4 MHz) BPF centric to the seed frequency at $f_1 = 1.25$ GHz. Due to the good FM efficiency, the detected fronthaul signal can directly drive the DBR section without extra RF driver, similar as in [30]. The spectral tuning characteristics of the DBR laser is reported in Fig. 4(a) as function of its DBR and gain currents. The excellent response of 14 GHz/mA to a change in DBR current I_{DBR} results in efficient FM. This property enables a large multiplication $M \in \{6 \dots 12\}$ when generating FR3-band carrier frequencies f_n and f_m for down- and uplink radio transmission, while only requiring a low-frequency seed at f_1 that yields $f_{n,m} = M f_1$. The power consumption of the DBR laser amounts to ~ 250 mW and is primarily determined by the static consumption of the gain section and its micro-Peltier element.

As the inset in Fig. 4(a) shows, an adjustment of the gain current I_{Gain} enables a fine-tuning of the emission wavelength. The discrete DBR modes of the laser can be clearly discerned by the hops of 79 GHz in optical frequency when continuously tuning the currents. For OFM operation, the FM drive will be set to remain within one mode, denoted as Ξ in Fig. 4(a).

Fig. 4. (a) Emission tuning of the DBR laser and (b) wideband RF comb generated through the OFM sub-system. The line Γ indicates the evolution of spectral notches when tuning the gain section of the DBR laser.

Optical frequency-to-intensity conversion is conducted using a periodic optical filter function. Such functions are well known from Mach-Zehnder interferometers (MZI), for which we will employ an MZI with a free spectral range (FSR) of 10 GHz. On top of this, we investigate the use of a more compact micro-ring resonator (MRR). This MRR is shown in Fig. 5(a). It uses a silicon-on-insulator waveguide with a cross-section of 220×500 nm². The waveguide-to-resonator coupling was optimized for a

propagation loss of 1 dB/cm for TE-like polarization. Coupling close to the critical-coupling condition was achieved with a bus-waveguide-to-MRR separation of $0.68 \mu\text{m}$. A meander-like design with a minimum bend radius of $15 \mu\text{m}$ reduces the footprint to $220 \times 2050 \mu\text{m}^2$ while maintaining an FSR similar to that of the MZI. The total length of the MRR is 7.92 mm. The through-port transmission characteristic is depicted in Fig. 5(b). It shows an actual FSR of 9.3 GHz and an extinction ratio of more than 10 dB. The optical bandwidth of the MRR is defined through the grating couplers that are employed to couple light to and from the photonic integrated circuit. The corresponding back-to-back transmission over a straight waveguide with two grating couplers indicates an optical fiber-to-fiber bandwidth of 33.9 nm at -3 dB.

Conversion to the electrical domain is conducted through a PIN photoreceiver with a power consumption of $\sim 80 \text{ mW}$. The high transimpedance gain ($\sim 4 \text{ k}\Omega$) levels the output signal of the OFM chain to a level that is compatible to feed the data up-conversion stage. The resulting RF-centric performance of the OFM sub-system will be discussed in Chapter V.A.

Fig. 5. (a) Silicon-on-insulator MRR device based on a 500-nm wide waveguide. The length of the meander-like resonator is 7.92 mm, with bends having a minimum radius of $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$. (b) Through-port transmission in comparison with a straight waveguide.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL FRAMEWORK

An experimental study has been conducted along 14 scenarios (Table I) that have been evaluated using the setup presented in Fig. 6. Data transmission throughout these scenarios is either based on a multi-carrier OFDM signal (OTA mode 1) transmitted at its intermediate frequency (IF) or a 1.25 Gb/s binary phase-shift keyed (BPSK) data stream (OTA mode 2). For the OFDM, an IF of 5 GHz has been chosen and 128 sub-carriers modulated by 64-point quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) are allocated over a signal bandwidth of 1 GHz. We have evaluated OFDM transmission in uplink direction while BPSK transmission over the FR3 channel has been evaluated in both, down- and uplink directions. For this purpose, frequency division duplexing (FDD) is applied in combination with a paired down-/uplink spectrum. However, the presented results do not restrict the use of alternative schemes, such as time division duplexing.

As described earlier, the TET connects to the RRH through an FR3 channel and reaches the CO after transport over a fiber-based fronthaul link (F). At the CO, two wavelength-multiplexed laser diodes (LD) serve the transmission of downlink data and the provision of a RRH seed at either f_1 (1.25 GHz) or $f_{n,m}$ (15/10 GHz) – according to the chosen scenario. The CO further includes a simple PIN+TIA based uplink receiver. Signal evaluation is based on bit error ratio testing (BERT) or off-line analysis of the error vector magnitude (EVM), whereas both performance indicators are evaluated as a function of the received optical power (ROP) along the mobile fronthaul. The latter includes a variable optical attenuator (VOA) for this purpose and is further furnished by ITU-T G.652B-compatible SMF. The directional split among down- and uplink at each end of the fronthaul link is made through red/blue (R/B) filters. The adoption of distinctive wavebands for down- and uplink ensures that the same SMF can be bidirectionally used, without being impaired by Rayleigh backscattering.

Fig. 6. Experimental setup. The inset shows the spectral allocation at the fronthaul for full-duplex FR3 BPSK transmission.

The experimental architecture of the RRH to evaluate all scenarios is shown in Fig. 7. The uplink FR3 signal that is received through the air interface is either down-converted to the baseband through RF delay demodulation (Mode 2) or converted to its IF frequency in case of OFDM (Mode 1). The converted signals are then transmitted over the fronthaul using a directly modulated laser (DML). Five implementation options have been evaluated for the local oscillator that is required for any frequency conversion at the RRH, as included in Table I. These options include a locally synthesized LO operating directly at a high conversion frequency $f_{n,m}$, a remoted high-frequency source $f_{n,m}$ that is transmitted from the CO by an electro-absorption modulated laser (EML), or the OFM stage shown in Fig. 3. For the latter, the seed frequency is either provided through a local RF source f_1 , a remoted centralized source whose frequency is transmitted from the CO using a low-bandwidth DML, or extracted from a baseband downlink data signal through use of the CR circuit. Either of these lower-frequency seeds at f_1 drives the OFM to generate higher-frequency RF carries $f_{n,m}$ for (i) translating the OFDM uplink frequency to its IF using an image-reject RF mixer, or (ii) to up-convert the baseband on-off keyed (OOK) downlink data signal D that is received through the fronthaul to the FR3 band by means of bi-phase modulation in a double-balanced RF mixer. The latter yields the BPSK representation used for over-the-air transmission of the data stream. In case that local RF sources are used at the RRH, a frequency synchronization signal (S) is distributed from the CO to the RRH through an auxiliary electrical 10-MHz reference. The RRH employs a duplexer (DPX) to implement the directional split at the air interface, for which ridged horn antennas were used at the RRH and TET to establish a directional lab-scale wireless link.

Fig. 7. Experimental architecture of the RRH.

The TET (Fig. 6) generates the multi-carrier radio signal employed to evaluate OTA mode 1, while it receives and remodulates the broadband signal subject to OTA mode 2. For the first, the generated OFDM is up-converted to its FR3-band carrier frequency f_m through an image-reject mixer. For the second, the received FR3 BPSK signal is down-converted from f_n to the baseband using either a local RF synthesizer (I in Fig. 6) or delay demodulation (II). To facilitate bidirectional transmission using single-carrier signals, an uplink FR3 carrier is re-generated. Two methods are compared for this purpose, including purely RF-based carrier reclamation (RFCR) and the OFM concept (IV). The RFCR chain (III) is appended to Fig. 6. It uses the received FR3 signal to establish a seed frequency of $f_x = 20$ GHz through self-mixing the incident signal. Subsequent frequency divider / multiplier stages ($\times 3/4$) then convert this seed to the target uplink frequency. In case of OFM, the demodulated downlink data is re-used to seed an OFM chain identical to that used at the RRH. The uplink data is again encoded through bi-phase modulation in a double-balanced RF mixer and transmitted towards the RRH.

TABLE I
EVALUATION SCENARIOS FOR BOTH OTA RADIO TRANSMISSION MODES.

Scenario	Data Stream			Central Office (CO)		Front-haul [km]	Remote Radio Head (RRH)		Tail-End Terminal (TET)		
	OTA radio format	FR3 DL [GHz]	FR3 UL [GHz]	spectral channels	remoted synthesizer [GHz]		local RF source [GHz]	10-MHz synchronization	down-conversion [GHz]	up-conversion [GHz]	
①	OTA mode 1	OFDM	–	15	–	–	$f_m = 10$	✓	–	$f_m = 15$, I/Q mixer	
②		OFDM	–	15	1λ	$f_m = 10$	seed	–	✗	$f_m = 15$, I/Q mixer	
③		OFDM	–	15	–	–	–	$f_1 = 1.25$	✓	–	$f_m = 15$, I/Q mixer
④		OFDM	–	15	2λ	$f_1 = 1.25$	seed	OFM ($M = 8$)	✗	–	$f_m = 15$, I/Q mixer
⑤		OFDM	–	15	–	–	–	$f_m = 10$	✗	–	$f_m = 15$, I/Q mixer
⑥		OFDM	–	15	2λ	$f_1 = 1.25$	14.3	OFM ($M = 8$)	✗	–	$f_m = 15$, I/Q mixer
⑦	OTA mode 2	BPSK	15	–	1λ	–	$f_n = 15$	✓	$f_n = 15$, mixer	–	
⑧		BPSK	15	–	1λ	–	14.3	$f_1 = 1.25$	✓	$f_n = 15$, mixer	–
⑨		BPSK	15	–	2λ	$f_1 = 1.25$	14.3	CR+OFM ($M=12$)	✗	$f_n = 15$, mixer	–
⑩		BPSK	15	–	1λ	–	14.3	CR+OFM ($M=12$)	✗	$f_n = 15$, mixer	–
⑪		BPSK	15	–	1λ (GbE)	–	14.3	CR+OFM ($M=12$)	✗	delay demod.	–
⑫		BPSK	10	–	1λ	–	–	$f_n = 10$	✗	delay demod.	–
⑬		BPSK	10	15	$(1+1)\lambda$	–	–	CR+OFM ($M=8$)	✗	delay demod.	RFCR, $f_m = 15$
⑭		BPSK	10	15	$(1+1)\lambda$	–	0→114	CR+OFM ($M=8$)	✗	delay demod.	OFM ($M = 12$), $f_m = 15$

V. RF GENERATION AND RADIO TRANSMISSION PERFORMANCE

We first discuss the performance of the OFM sub-system, before elaborating on the radio transmission in both OTA modes and bidirectional, remodulated FR3-band transmission.

A. Carrier Generation through OFM

Figure 4(b) reports the generated RF comb spectrum of the OFM stage, before the target FR3 carrier frequency $f_{n,m}$ is selected. The evolution of comb lines is presented as function of the gain current I_{Gain} of the DBR laser, which allows for a spectral alignment to the demodulating optical filter with a fine tuning at $\kappa_{\text{opt}} \approx -0.54$ GHz/mA. As it is evident from Fig. 4(b), this tuning tailors the optical spectrum to pronounce optical comb lines that match the desired multiplication factor M , before the overall beat spectrum is converted to the RF domain. The generated RF carriers, which are spaced by $f_1 = 1.25$ GHz, therefore feature a periodic power transfer among them when detuning I_{Gain} . This effect is indicated by the dashed line (Γ) that follows the evolution of spectral notches along neighboring RF carriers at a gain-section drive of $\kappa_{\text{RF}} = -2$ mA/GHz, corresponding to a 1:1 translation between RF and optical frequency domains that requires $\kappa_{\text{opt}} \cdot \kappa_{\text{RF}} = 1$. With this, a specific RF carrier $f_{n,m}$ can be enhanced to select a specific FR3 sub-band for wireless radio signal transmission.

Fig. 8. (a) RF phase noise for various RF carriers and (b) its dependence on ROP and longer-term stability. (c) RF phase noise for FR3 carrier generation for a target frequency range from 7.5 to 15 GHz.

The RF phase noise Φ_{RF} on OFM-generated carriers is presented in Fig. 8(a) when applying a seed f_1 that is received through the fronthaul at a ROP of -10 dBm. Compared to a local RF synthesizer that generates a 10-GHz LO at the RRH (\blacklozenge), we see a jitter-imposed increase of 9.2 dB at 250 kHz for the recovered clock harmonic that is extracted by the utilized Gigabit-Ethernet (GbE) grade CR circuit (\blacksquare). This stimulus incident to the OFM stage is further shaped in its phase noise by the bandpass range of the cleaning filter (T_{BPF}) located at OFM input. Frequency multiplication through the MZI-based OFM chain leads to a penalty of 15.8 dB (\blacktriangle), which is attributed to the 8-fold multiplication to reach $f_n = 10$ GHz and added noise during photodetection. The MRR-assisted OFM (\blacktriangle) performs similarly, with a difference of 1.6 dB in Φ_{RF} .

When applying RFCR for the bidirectional transmission scheme to obtain an uplink carrier at $f_m = 15$ GHz at the TET derived

from the received FR3 downlink BPSK signal, we experience another 7.7 dB of degradation, leading to $\Phi_{\text{RF}} = -76.4$ dBc/Hz at 250 kHz (●). A similar phase noise applies when instead using the OFM chain at the TET (□). Even though this noise is too high to accommodate the multi-carrier OFDM format used in OTA mode 1, these reclaimed FR3 carriers suit the needs for single-carrier uplink signal transmission – as will be proven shortly.

Figure 8(b) reports the phase noise of the generated FR3 downlink carrier of $f_n = 10$ GHz (▲) at 250 kHz from its carrier frequency, as a function of the ROP for the fronthaul seed f_1 . A 3-dB penalty in Φ_{RF} is incurred when the ROP drops below -18.1 dBm. Given the typical (virtual) point-to-point nature of fronthaul links, this result indicates a sufficiently high power margin before incurring phase noise degradation. Moreover, the continuous acquisition of the phase noise (ζ) at this ROP over 6 hours proves a stable OFM operation.

Figure 8(c) further demonstrates wideband OFM operation. FR3-band carriers from 7.5 to 15 GHz have been generated, showing a peak-to-peak phase noise deviation of only 5.9 dB at 250 kHz – despite operation over a full octave.

Fig. 9. (a) EVM performance for multi-carrier radio transmission in OTA mode 1. (b) Response of the SMF-based fronthaul for remote f_m supply. (c) EVM as a function of the sub-carrier spacing ζ . (d) Uplink OFDM spectrum received at the CO.

B. Multi-Carrier Radio Transmission (OTA Mode 1)

Figure 9(a) presents the EVM performance for the six scenarios relevant to OTA mode 1 (Table I). Reference is first made to the OFM-less case where a synchronized LO (f_n) at the RRH (scenario ①) feeds the down-conversion of the FR3 uplink OFDM signal. Here, an EVM of 3.7% is accomplished before fronthaul transmission (point p in Fig. 7.) In scenario ②, the same 10-GHz LO has been remoted by the CO through the fronthaul. For this, an EML is used as LD at the CO and the received down-conversion carrier f_m is bypassed along the OFM stage. We notice dispersion-induced fading [31] in this case, which leads to a partial (EML2) and deep fading (EML1) for the transported carrier, depending on the exact EML model. This fading is characterized in Fig. 9(b) through the channel response of the 14.3-km fronthaul span. It causes a large EVM penalty of 3.9% (EML2) and 7% (EML1) at a ROP of -8 dBm, even after re-amplifying the received carrier f_m . When instead applying OFM to locally generate f_m with a local seed source f_1 at the RRH (scenario ③), we achieve the same low EVM as when utilizing a synchronized local RF synthesizer operating at f_m . When the low-frequency seed f_1 is transported from the CO (scenario ④) while the performance of the down-converted OFDM radio signal is still analyzed at the RRH (p), the same low EVM of 3.6% as in scenario ① can be accomplished. This is a result of the much lower seed frequency $f_1 < f_m$, which mitigates a dispersion-induced penalty. An EVM penalty of 1% is incurred once the ROP of the optically transported seed falls below -9.4 dBm (●).

Figure 9(c) discusses the impact of a reduced OFDM sub-carrier spacing ζ on the EVM. Results are shown for a constant 1-GHz OFDM bandwidth and a seed with a ROP of -7 dBm. We see a rising penalty (▲) with respect to a locally synthesized f_n (●) once ζ falls below 600 kHz. Moreover, Fig. 9(c) emphasizes the need of synchronizing local synthesizers at the RRH to a centralized clock at the CO: Without this synchronization (scenario ⑤) through an electrical 10-MHz link between CO and RRH (S in Fig. 6), an EVM penalty of 3% to 6.2% applies (×). In case of OFM (scenario ④), no such synchronization is required for the RRH equipment.

End-to-end uplink transmission including radio transport over the mobile fronthaul (scenario ⑥) using a common optical link loss setting for the remotely supplied feed f_1 and the down-converted uplink radio signal leads to an additional EVM penalty of <2% for a ROP larger than -11 dBm (▲). Figure 9(d) shows the down-converted OFDM signal spectrum at its IF of 5 GHz, together with the EVM of all sub-carriers (SC), at a ROP of -8 dBm to the CO. The EVM antenna limit of 8% for 64-QAM transmission is reached at -11.4 dBm – which together with the optical signal launch of 6 dBm allows to accommodate a fronthaul budget of 17.4 dB, despite the use of simple PIN+TIA receivers at both end-points of the link.

Figure 10(a) reports a long-term EVM acquisition for scenario ⑥. The spectral setup within the OFM chain, which is made through the DBR constants I_{DBR} and I_{Gain} , remains stable under lab conditions – even without active bias control. The EVM performance remains clearly below the 8% antenna limit for the entire duration of more than 3 hours and does not show signs of spurious EVM artifacts. This stability is also reflected in the post-FEC data rate R . Attributing for higher modulation efficiencies

of >6 bit/symbol that can be achieved due to the good EVM performance, R swings between 6.4 and 5.5 Gb/s, meaning a fluctuation of 13.6% in peak data rate.

Fig. 10. (a) Longer-term EVM in OTA mode 1 when employing OFM. (b) BER performance in OTA mode 2 for BPSK transmission at 15 GHz and various RF management strategies. (c) Longer-term GbE throughput and (d) BER for RF down-converting receiver. (e) BER and eye when employing delay demodulation at the TET.

C. Broadband BPSK Transmission (OTA Mode 2)

Figure 10(b) presents the BER performance for scenarios 7 to 10, which apply to OTA mode 2 (Table I). Results are reported for end-to-end transmission involving fronthaul and lab-scale wireless link operated at an FR3-band carrier frequency of 15 GHz. Since there is no IF involved in OTA mode 2, this setting corresponds to $f_n = 15$ GHz. A downlink BER of $<10^{-6}$ can be accomplished for a ROP larger than -22.6 dBm to the RRH when using the data-seeded FR3-band carrier generation method (scenario 10) utilizing the CR and OFM (\blacktriangle). The low BER is evidenced through the clearly open eye diagram at the TET receiver. A dynamic ROP range of >15 dB (Δ in Fig. 10(b)) can be obtained. There is no improvement when using a local FR3-band RF synthesizer to generate f_n (\blacksquare , scenario 7) or any other RF management methods involving a local seed f_1 in combination with OFM (\square , scenario 8), or remote seeding of f_1 (\bullet , scenario 9). This indicates that the end-to-end performance is limited by a cut-off in reception sensitivity at the RRH data receiver, especially with respect to the ability of the CR circuit to regenerate the OOK data transported over the fronthaul. This proves the negligible impact of RF phase noise incurred through CR and OFM.

Besides evaluating the BER, we have further conducted real-time traffic measurements by feeding a GbE downlink over the hybrid optical / FR3 link (scenario 11) through use of electro-optic converters serving as protocol terminators at the CO and TET, respectively (Fig. 6). As reported in Fig. 10(c), the obtained GbE throughput R is above 0.81 (0.77) Gb/s for 95% (99%) of the measurements. We noticed a few drops in the GbE rate, as they also appear in the consecutively acquired longer-term real-time BER acquisition of Fig. 10(d), where values above 10^{-8} sporadically occur. These BER excursions are attributed to phase instabilities in the wireless RF path, which cause a phase detuning between the FR3-band carrier generated at the RRH and that locally synthesized at the TET when down-converting the FR3 BPSK signal to the baseband. For this reason, the down-conversion of the FR3-band BPSK signal at the TET has been substituted by delay demodulation. With this, the BER remained at a value below 10^{-9} for the entire measurement duration of 180 min (Fig. 10(e)). This proves the stability of the overall FR3-band transmission and in particular that of the data-seeded and OFM-assisted RF carrier generation method employed at the RRH.

Fig. 11. (a) Signal spectra along the RF chain for full-duplex down/uplink BPSK radio transmission at FR3 frequencies of 10/15 GHz. (b) BER performance for downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) as a function of the ROP at the RRH and CO, respectively.

D. Full-Duplex BiDi BPSK Transmission (OTA Mode 2)

Bidirectional full-duplex BPSK transmission over the FR3 band has been investigated in combination with a paired down-/uplink spectrum at $f_n = 10$ GHz and $f_m = 15$ GHz, respectively. This extension of OTA mode 2 is covered through scenarios 12 to 14. The corresponding RF signal spectra at the RRH and the TET are reported in Fig. 11(a), together with the FDD transmission T_{DPX} that result from the duplexers at the antennas to shape the paired down-/uplink FR3 bands. The signal spectra include the detected optical downlink signal (α), the extracted clock (β), the OFM-generated downlink carrier f_n at the RRH (γ), the transmitted FR3 downlink signal (δ), the received downlink at the TET without (ϵ) and with (φ) simultaneous FR3 uplink transmission and the demodulated downlink data before (η) and after (χ) baseband filtering. Further shown are the FR3 uplink carrier f_m resulting from the TET-side OFM (μ) and the transmitted uplink radio signal (ν) that is received by the RRH (π), where it is demodulated to the baseband (θ).

Figure 11(b) reports the optical back-to-back BER for full-duplex down- and uplink FR3 BPSK transmission as a function of the ROP at the RRH and CO. As a baseline, we consider downlink reception with RF-based up-conversion at the RRH, using a local RF synthesizer for synchronized carrier generation at $f_n = 10$ GHz at the RRH. For this reference scenario 12, a reception sensitivity of -19.2 dBm is obtained at a BER of 10^{-10} (◆). When performing downlink carrier generation with CR and OFM (scenarios 13 and 14), the sensitivity slightly degrades by 0.5 and 0.9 dB for utilizing the MZI (●) and the compact MRR (△) within the OFM chain. Moreover, a dynamic range of >20 dB can be supported.

The uplink performance is not impacted by a significant penalty with respect to the downlink, even though its carrier is reclaimed from the downlink radio: For scenario 13, which employs the RFCR method at the TET, a sensitivity of -18.2 dBm is obtained (■). This relates to a small 1-dB penalty with respect to the baseline (◆). There is no penalty incurred in scenario 14, when an MZI-based OFM is instead adopted at the TET (□) – in addition to the already utilized MRR-based OFM at the RRH. Given the optical launch power of 8.2 / 10.5 dBm for the optical down- / uplink at CO and RRH, respectively, a large optical budget of 26.5 dB is supported. These results confirm the reclamation efficiency of the OFM scheme to facilitate full-duplex FR3-band transmission.

Figure 12(a) discusses the down- (●) and uplink (■) BER over the fronthaul reach, without extra loss due to a VOA. Long fiber spans are supported between the CO and RRH due to baseband transmission, meaning that the performance is merely determined by the loss limit. To verify this, the supported optical back-to-back budget that has been acquired through Fig. 11(b) has been translated into an expected fiber reach, considering begin-of-life (BOL: 0.342 / 0.212 dB/km at 1320 / 1550 nm) and end-of-life (EOL: 0.415 / 0.277 dB/km) fiber losses and including a connector loss of 0.2 dB per lab fiber spool (12-15 km each). The operational windows for these loss limits of down- and uplink are shown in Fig. 12(a) as dashed regions. The experimental BER agrees well with this estimation: A downlink BER below 10^{-10} can be supported for more than 85 km (●), before it exceeds these “error-free” conditions. For the uplink, this point is reached earlier, after 70 km (■), which is explained by the higher O-band fiber loss.

For additional comparison with up-converted radio-over-fiber transmission, Fig. 12(a) includes an estimation for the fading of a 10-GHz RF carrier (f_n) that is transmitted as double-sideband signal over the mobile fronthaul. A significant dispersion-induced power fading of 10 dB occurs as the fiber length exceeds 30 km, as confirmed through experimental data on RF power loss (×). This emphasizes once more the advantage of simplified baseband transmission.

Finally, Fig. 12(b) evaluates the stability of the full-duplex FR3 link. The BER has been continuously taken over more than 1 hour for a ROP that sets a margin of 1 dB to the slightly worse uplink sensitivity. The error-free condition (BER < 10^{-9}) has been violated for a small percentage of 0.26% and 0.36% in case of down- (●) and uplink (■) transmission, respectively.

Fig. 12. (a) Downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) BER performance as a function of the fronthaul reach. (b) Longer-term BER performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated FR3-band transmission in combination with centralized RF management, OFM-enabled frequency synthesis and adaptive modulation. While the first enables us to retain data and frequency references at the fronthaul segment within a low and thus fading-agnostic frequency range below 1.25 GHz, as evidenced for a fiber reach up to 70 km and optical budgets of >17 dB, an adaptive modulation scheme can simplify OTA transmission through use of DSP-free signaling. Towards that, we have confirmed the availability of frequency-flat FR3 windows for directional point-to-point links, which in combination with the spectral flexibility inherent to OFM-based frequency synthesis can facilitate single-carrier radio transmission – as shown for DSP-free 1 Gb/s BPSK transmission. Moreover, full-duplex bidirectional single-carrier transmission over a paired FR3-band spectrum has been demonstrated based on an OFM-assisted carrier recovery at the TET, while a penalty-free simplification of the OFM sub-system has been investigated through use of a compact silicon micro-ring resonator.

Given the requirements and characteristics of the OFM stage in terms of amplification and power consumption, we consider its performance to fall close to that of a purely RF-based approach, which is subject to high conversion loss during frequency multiplication and difficulties in scaling up the multiplication factor. Due to this limitation, the advantage of the OFM-based approach is expected to become more emphasized when addressing higher output carrier frequencies in the FR2- or FR3-bands. To reach these frequency bands while ensuring coverage of the full FR3-band up to 24.25 GHz, optical FM emitters with higher bandwidths up to 10 GHz will be required. Though not available for our current work, the feasibility of such elevated DBR bandwidths has been demonstrated elsewhere [32].

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